

Supplementary Materials for

ArcGIS-Based Digital Geological Mapping in the Holy Cross Mountains (Poland)

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A. Comparison of Geoinformatics and Geophysics in Geoenvironment and Applied Geology and Exploration Geology programmes during first 2 years of undergraduate studies before field course of geological mapping (*- only for selected specialization; peach colour marks field courses).

Type of course	Digital field course		Classical field course			
Study program	Geoinformatics and Geophysics in Geoenvironment		Applied Geology		Exploration Geology	
Field of study	Subject	Hours (lectures + laboratories)	Subject	Hours or days (lectures + laboratories)	Subject	Hours (lectures + laboratories)
Informatics and GIS	Introduction to informatics	60	Information technology in geology and GIS fundamentals	45	Information technology in geology and GIS fundamentals	45
	Geographic Information Systems GIS I	30				
	Geographic Information Systems GIS II	45				
	Geographic Information Systems GIS III	45				
	Python programming tools for data analysis	60				
Summary		240		45		45
Geological subjects preparing to geological mapping	Basic of geology	120	Dynamic geology	120	Dynamic geology	150
			Spatial geometry	60	Spatial geometry	60
	Geological mapping with GIS components	45	Geological mapping	60	Geological mapping	60
	Introduction to engineering geology	45	Basic engineering geology	60		
	Soil and rock mechanics	30	Mechanics and strength of materials	60		
			Soil science	75		
	Geomorphology and Quaternary geology	30	Geomorphology and Quaternary geology	60	Geomorphology and Quaternary geology	120
					Practical training – geology outside the classroom	30
			Historical geology	60	Historical geology	150
		Structural geology	60	Structural geology	60	

			Mineralogy	60	Mineralogy	150
			Paleontology I	60	Paleontology I	60
					Paleontologia II	30
			sedimentology	60*	sedimentology	60
	Field course in Geological Mapping with GIS components	11 days	Field course in general geology	19 days	Field course in general geology	19 days
			Field course in historical geology	5 days	Field course in historical geology	5 days
			Field course in geomorphology and Quaternary geology	4 days	Field course in geomorphology and Quaternary geology	5 days
Summary		270 hours, 11 days		795 hours, 28 days		930 hours, 29 days
Geodesy	Geodetic Fundamentals in Information Systems	60	Geodesy	60	Geodesy	60
Geofizyka	Basics of applied geophysics	45	Introduction to geophysics	30*	Introduction to geophysics	30
	Electrical resistivity methods	45				
	Ground-penetrating radar (GPR) method	15				
	Seismic method	45				
	Gravimetry and magnetics	15				
	Geophysical methods in geoengineering	5 days				
Hydrology	Hydrological Processes and Phenomena	45	Hydrogeology	60	Hydrology	30
	Basics of hydrogeology	45	Hydrology and hydraulics	45*	Hydrogeology for exploration geology	60
	Mathematics	120	Mathematics	120		
Other subjects	Physics	45	Physics	45		
			Chemistry	75	Chemistry	75
	Geostatistical methods in geoengineering	30	Geochemistry	30	Geochemistry	30
					Mathematics for exploration geology	60
			Environmental protection and management	60		
			Basics of statistics	60	Basics of statistics	60

B. Anonymous student opinions about application of ArcGIS software and Field Maps for mobile device during the digital geological mapping course.

Student 1

The digital mapping method used in the course proved to significantly accelerate the workflow compared to traditional methods. The area originally projected to take over a dozen days—based on the average time of students using conventional techniques—was completed in nearly half the time. This shift allowed students to focus more on 'thinking' rather than just 'doing,' reducing the physical workload and expanding the opportunity for cognitive analysis.

Student 2

I think that using ArcGIS and Field Maps really improved our geological mapping. The phone app made it simple to find and log points—being able to attach photos and save layers directly on-site saved a lot of time. Making the final maps on a

computer afterwards was also way easier because the field data was so well-organized. This is definitely the way to go for the future; it's already much better than the old paper-and-pen method, and I can see even more potential for improvement.

Student 3

Using ArcGIS software and the Field Maps app demonstrated the practical potential of technology. Because we conducted our work using both traditional methods (with a pencil) and digital ones, we were able to compare the two approaches and observe their respective pros and cons. Introducing digital methods into courses highlights the benefits of available technology—a field where, in geology, the potential of digital tools is often not fully realized.

Student 4

In my opinion, using the ArcGIS environment and Field Maps drastically speeds up fieldwork. To be honest, having these tools at my disposal, I simply cannot imagine doing it any other way. The applications themselves are very intuitive and certainly future-proof.

Student 5

I think that, with proper system preparation, this is undoubtedly a huge improvement in recording fieldwork findings. The system was definitely well-prepared and accounted for all/most variables. An additional notes field was also available, ensuring no details were missed. The biggest improvement was the GPS tracking capability.

Student 6

In my opinion, the digital method we used significantly accelerated the process of drilling documentation and its subsequent editing. The Field Maps app allowed us to create documentation points on the fly, without having to use a whole range of tools such as pencils, crayons, or pens.

Despite the fact that we had less geological knowledge than our colleagues from GEP and GES, we were able to create more points per day than they did, mainly thanks to the Field Maps app.

Another positive aspect was that the leaders could see our route and documentation points in real time on their phones, which made it easier for them to, among other things, find us in the field and correct any mistakes.

Also, during small-scale work on attachments at the center, I felt that we were able to create maps, explanations, and so on faster than they did. ArcGIS projects could be corrected and edited at any time with just a few clicks, whereas with paper maps you'd have to fumble with erasers or even redraw the entire map. ArcGIS was simply much more efficient in this regard.

Student 7

The use of digital geological mapping using ArcGIS software and the ArcGIS Field Maps application proved very useful during the course. These tools accelerated fieldwork and facilitated data recording and visualization, as well as its subsequent transfer for further analysis on a computer. However, a significant limitation is the need to maintain a constant connection – losing it during work, for example, while adding points, could result in the measurement not being saved.

Student 8

The introduction of the Field Maps application was a huge improvement. It's a specific tool that's actually being used in the industry today, especially by young people entering the job market. Unfortunately, that's where the positives end. Although we were already well-versed in ArcGIS Pro at this stage of our studies, we weren't able to utilize it at a satisfactory level. A significant emphasis was placed on ArcGIS Online, which is very limited and simply doesn't allow for serious project work. We had no opportunity to demonstrate our analysis of the collected data.

There was no room for automating work using short Python scripts, utilizing spatial analysis libraries, or learning new specialized software that could develop our skills in the field we were interested in. Instead of building interesting models based on field data, which would have been a natural part of our studies, we stuck to the most basic functions, which didn't enhance our geoinformatics knowledge. Considering that the course takes place during the summer holidays, depriving students of time for rest or paid work, this is quite disappointing. Instead of developing geoinformatics skills, we are stuck in purely geological dilemmas, which, according to our studies, should not be a priority.